

Long-term data for Europe

EURHISFIRM

D1.13: Final yearly documentation and minutes of project meetings

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I. Introduction

During the third year of the project, the project members continued to engage with each other through a number of different meetings. These took place via telephone, video conferencing, or face-to-face. In general, these meetings can be divided into two different categories: operational and governance/strategy.

Meeting category	Meeting type	Method(s)	Frequency
1. Operational	Work Packages	Online	Variable
	WGIS (Work Group on Identification and Standards)	Online	Bi-weekly
2. Governance/strategy	Executive committee	Online	Monthly, bi-monthly
	Steering committee	Online	Every trimester
	General assembly and the Project Advisory Board	Online	Yearly

The second annual Project Advisory Board (PAB) and General Assembly meeting, which falls under the “Governance/strategy” category, was originally scheduled for May 2020 and was postponed/held in October 2020 due to the Covid-19 pandemic.

Additionally, an informational meeting in Brussels for interested and potential external stakeholders was originally scheduled on 24 March 2020. This was originally postponed due to the situation caused by Covid-19, but due to the continuing difficult circumstances, has been effectively cancelled.

This report documents the main content of the different types of meetings that have been realised during the third year. At the same time, this report will not reproduce the detailed contents/minutes of each meeting, because the abundance of these precise details would not be interesting or insightful for this report’s audience. Instead, we are using this report as an opportunity to share the current meeting organisations and important contents.

II. Meeting contents/minutes

During the year, the main contents/decisions of the different types of meetings have been the following:

1. Operational meetings

Work Packages

These meetings are conducted within and across Work Packages and institutions to advance operational progress. As noted in the above table, the meetings were held exclusively in the format of video conferencing due to the challenging conditions of the global pandemic. Some Work Packages hold regular,

periodical meetings for longer-term tasks, while other Work Packages organise their meetings on an as-needed basis. In order to facilitate project coherence, some Work Packages include the project manager in the meetings. Additionally, the work packages hold catchup meetings with the project manager as necessary.

WGIS (Work Group on Identification and Standards)

In the second year of the project, according to the conclusions made at the first General Assembly in 2019, there was a consensus to encourage more inter-Work package and/or inter-institutional collaborations. In particular, this need was highlighted within Work packages 5-7 and 9, or the more “technical” Work packages of the project. In January 2020, a face-to-face meeting was held among these “technical” colleagues of the project, where each work package shared its progress so far. A discussion was then held on how to synchronise the work among these groups going forward and to potentially change the communication practices in place. The WGIS group continued to play a crucial role in coordinating key issues across the technical work packages in 2021 with their regularly held meetings. They also fulfilled the knowledge sharing priorities by sending around their deliverables to this group. The work packages involved are primarily 4, 5, 6, 7, and 9.

2. Governance and strategy meetings

Executive Committee

The Executive Committee meets on a monthly basis (exclusively via video conferencing since the Covid-19 pandemic). The members consist of: Angelo Riva (École d'Économie de Paris), Jan Annaert (Universiteit Antwerpen), and Wolfgang König (Goethe-Universität Frankfurt). The meetings are also accompanied by the project manager (based at the École d'Économie de Paris) for purposes of alignment with the Executive Committee's decisions with the project and the work packages as a whole.

In the final year of the project, the meetings covered similar topics of governance and project direction/management as the previous meetings, but with additional focus on issues related to the completion of the project in light of the Covid-19 pandemic. The meetings also prioritised the design of the project's final reports.

Steering Committee

The Steering Committee meets every trimester. In the final year of the project, these meetings also took place exclusively via video conferencing due to the pandemic. The participants consist of the work package leaders (the Executive Committee members are thus inherently members of the Steering Committee). The Steering Committee meetings are also attended by the project manager (to ensure alignment of the project strategy among the Executive Committee, the Steering Committee, and the Work Packages), as well as other relevant person(s) for the agenda at hand (for example, if a particular topic/concept will be discussed and will be presented by a project team member). The meeting topics are governance- and strategy-related, with a greater emphasis to the technical and content implementation of the project and the consortium coordination overall.

In the final year of the project, the meetings also prioritised the future direction of the project, as well as agreement on the features of the project's final design and the reports.

Project Advisory Board (PAB) and General Assembly

The Project Advisory Board (PAB) meets yearly, in conjunction with the General Assembly. The PAB provides feedback on the project progress and advises on key strategic questions. These serve as crucial perspectives upon the project's overall direction and governance. The General Assembly is an extension of the PAB meeting, which summarises the issues discussed within the PAB and opens the discussion to the external invited guests and interested stakeholders. This meeting also includes further detailed progress on the work completed and is an important opportunity for feedback and alignment from the entire consortium on these advancements.

The first annual Project Advisory Board (PAB) and General Assembly (GA) meeting was held at the Wroclaw University of Economics and Business (work package 2 lead beneficiary) in March 2019. The second annual PAB and GA meeting was originally scheduled slightly after the first 24 months of the project, to take place in May 2020 at the Queen's University of Belfast (work package 8 lead beneficiary) and organised together with the Wroclaw University of Economics and Business. However, due to the current Covid-19 pandemic, this meeting was postponed to October 2020 in an online format (video conferencing). This meeting held a different format than the previous edition of the GA. Instead of presenting each work package's accomplishments, the second edition of the GA sought to present the inter-work package cooperation, which was one of the feedback of the PAB at the previous edition (i.e. stronger inter-work package should be a priority). The format of this meeting therefore centred around the main themes and challenges of the project that will be addressed in the final reports, such as data management and production; the common data standardisations; the business model and governance; EURHISFIRM's participation and coherence with the SSHOC (Social Science and Humanities Open Cloud) project and the EOSC (European Open Science Cloud) framework. The results of this meeting has shaped the final reports of the project.

The final PAB meeting was held on the 7th of June 2021 (online due to the pandemic). They provided feedback on the final report draft (approved) as well as other points for discussion, which were then continued in the final General Assembly which was held on the 17th of June 2021 (online due to the pandemic). The General Assembly was attended by EURHISFIRM project members, the PAB members, as well as guests (interested partners in joining the consortium for phase II as well as other practitioners from relevant organisations).

III. Conclusions

In the third and final year of the project, the communications and the logistics were especially challenged by the global pandemic, which prevented face-to-face meetings from taking place. This led to postponement of some key meetings, such as the PAB and GA meetings, as well as the changing of the formats from physical meetings to exclusively online. However, in spite of these difficulties, the project managed to proceed by adapting to these new ways of organisation for the different types of meetings.